

Study of Phytochemical Analysis of *Boerhaavia diffusa* and *Tribulus terrestris* for the Kidney Disorder

Dr. Alpa K. Patel

Department of Botany, SICES Degree College of Arts, Science & Commerce, Ambernath – Thane .
 Maharashtra

Email- alpap25@gmail.com

Abstract:

Plants are rich source of crude drug for therapeutic purpose. The traditional knowledge of these herbal recipes is popular among the indigenous and local communities. While in cities people are lacking behind. Kidney failure is a major problem in now days. A person with less than 10 to 15% kidney function needs to have Dialysis or kidney transplant. *Boerhaavia diffusa* and *Tribulus terrestris*, both are mainly used for treating the disorders of kidneys, some common Bio active compounds are responsible for the curing the kidney disorders. Still 80% of the plants are not characterized as per their phytochemical constituents and thus they are not utilized as per their medicinal value.

Key Words: *Boerhaavia diffusa*, *Tribulus terrestris*, Phytochemical Analysis, Kidney Disorder, natural drug

Introduction:

Boerhaavia diffusa belonging to Nyctaginaceae family, commonly known as 'Punarnava' in the Indian system of Ayurvedic medicine, it is a perennial creeping herb commonly found throughout the waste land of India. This plant is especially useful for treating all the disorders of the kidneys. It also acts as a liver tonic and can be used to treat all the disorders of the liver.

Tribulus terrestris is an annual plants belonging to the family Zygophyllaceae also known as Gokhru in India, has been used as an ancient herb for thousands of years. It has been the most used plant as medicine in

India for ages. People use the fruit, leaf, and root as therapeutic medicine for wide-ranging diseases. *Tribulus terrestris* is an herb that deals with urinary tract infection and kidney problems. It is famous for its diuretic properties also.

Rationale of the study:

The findings of the chemical constituents from plants would provide the basis for developing the new lead molecules in favour of natural product drug discovery, which is beneficial to pharmaceutical point of view. Application of same will also helpful to Ayurveda, Homeopathy and Tissue culture.

Table I: Ethnomedical uses of *Boerhaavia diffusa* by various countries

Name of the Country	Ethnomedical uses
Brazil	for albuminuria, beri-beri, bile insufficiency, cystitis, edema, gallbladder problems, gallstones, gonorrhoea, guinea worms, hepatitis, hypertension, jaundice, kidney disorders, kidney stones, liver disorders, liver support, nephritis, renal disorders, sclerosis (liver), snakebite, spleen (enlarged), urinary disorders, urinary retention
Guatemala	for erysipelas, guinea worms
India	for abdominal pain, anemia, ascites, asthma, blood purification, cancer, cataracts, childbirth, cholera, constipation, cough, debility, digestive sluggishness, dropsy, dyspepsia, edema, eye problems, fever, gonorrhoea, guinea worms, heart ailments, heart disease, hemorrhages (childbirth), hemorrhages (thoracic), hemorrhoids, inflammation (internal), internal parasites, jaundice, kidney disorders, kidney stones, lactation aid, liver disorders, liver support, menstrual disorders, renal insufficiency, rheumatism, snakebite, spleen (enlarged), urinary disorders, weakness, and as a diuretic and expectorant
Iran	for edema, gonorrhoea, hives, intestinal gas, jaundice, joint pain, lumbago, nephritis, and as an appetite stimulant, diuretic and expectorant
Nigeria	for abscesses, asthma, boils, convulsions, epilepsy, fever, guinea worms, and as an expectorant and laxative
West Africa	for abortion, guinea worms, menstrual irregularities, and as an aphrodisiac
Philippines	Diuretic, fever, purgative and vermifuge
Ghana	Asthma and Boils
Elsewhere	for childbirth, guinea worms, jaundice, sterility, yaws

Objectives:

The following are the objectives of Research:

1. To find out the Secondary metabolites from *Boerhaavia diffusa* and *Tribulus terrestris*.
2. To check the presence of the common bioactive compounds from *Boerhaavia diffusa* and *Tribulus terrestris*.
3. Analysis of those bioactive compounds.
4. To cultivate both the plants to get maximum Secondary metabolites for further study.

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Hypothesis:

The further advances of this project can help us get the common bioactive compounds in bulk amount for making highly efficient natural drug so as to get quick remedies and relief to kidney patients. Artificial cultivation can also be done where soil is not favourable for the growth of the plant. Further the common bioactive compounds can be obtained in larger quantity by controlling soil condition, which will helpful for researchers in finding a highly efficient natural drug for kidney patients without any side effects.

Methods & Materials:

Work plan:

Methodology: Solvent Extraction

Extraction is the separation of medicinally active parts of plant tissues using selective solvents through standard process. These plant based constituents can be derived from

any part of the plant like bark, leaves, flowers, roots, fruits, seeds, etc.

Collection and preparation of plant materials:

Whole plant of *Boerhaavia diffusa* and *Tribulus terrestris* were collected. The dried plant samples are ground to fine powder with mortar and pestle. The main purpose of drying is to remove the water content from plants so that the plants can be stored. Plants need to be dried immediately as soon as the plants collection finish otherwise this it will leads to spoilage of plant materials. Powder extracted using Methanol by Plant tissue homogenization.

Collection of Plants Cleaning and Drying of Plants

The leaves of the *Tribulus terrestris* were collected from, Moletha, Vadodara , Gujarat , India and brought to laboratory. Plant parts leaves were cleaned by washing with distilled water to remove dust, and other contaminants. The leaves were shade dried into laboratory at room temperature at 30°C for 10 days. The dried leaves were grounded to make fine powder. Powder of samples were kept in air tight containers.

The leaves of the *Boerhaavia diffusa* were collected from, Rayasan, Gandhinagar, Gujarat , India and brought to laboratory. Plant parts leaves were cleaned by washing with distilled water to remove dust, and other contaminants. The leaves were shade dried into laboratory at room temperature at 30°C for 10 days. The dried leaves were grounded to make fine powder. Powdered samples were kept in air tight containers.

Fig. I -*Boerhaavia diffusa*

Tribulus terrestris

Each dried plant sample was ground and extracted with methanol. 20 gm of powder was soaked into 200 ml of methanol. The extraction process was carried out for 48 hours at room temperature on orbital shaker.

Methods of Extraction

Plant Tissue Homogenization

Plant tissue homogenization in solvent has been used by many researchers. Dried or wet, fresh parts of plant are grinded in a blender

to fine particles, add in a certain quantity of solvent and shaken vigorously for 5 - 10 min or left for 24 hrs after which the extract is filtered through the define process. The filtrate then dried under reduced pressure and re-dissolved in the mentioned solvent to determine the concentration of solution. Some researchers however centrifuged the filtrate for better clarification of the plant extract. Addition of water to alcohol improves extraction rate significantly, methanol is the best solvent for polyphenol extraction

Phytochemical screening:

Phytochemical examinations were carried out for the plant - extracts as per the standard methods.

Detection of alkaloids: Plant -Extracts were dissolved individually in dil. Hydrochloric acid and filtered by define process.

a) Mayer's Test: Test - Plant -Extracts were treated with Mayer's reagent (Potassium Mercuric Iodide). Formation of a yellow coloured precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids in a plant .

b)Wagner's Test: Plant -Extracts were treated with Wagner's reagent (Iodine in Potassium Iodide). Formation of brown or reddish precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids in a plant extract.

c)Dragendroff's Test: Plant -Extracts were treated with Dragendroff's reagent (solution of Potassium Bismuth Iodide). Formation of red precipitate shows the presence of alkaloids.

d)Hager's Test: Plant -Extracts were treated with Hager's reagent (saturated picric acid solution). Presence of alkaloids confirmed by the formation of yellow coloured precipitate in a solution.

2. Detection of glycosides: Plant -Extracts were hydrolysed with dilute HCl, and then used to test for glycosides.

a) Modified Borntrager's Test: Plant -Extracts were treated with Ferric Chloride solution and keep in boiling water for about 5 minutes. The mixture was cooled and then extracted with equal volumes of benzene. The benzene layer was taken out and treated with ammonia solution. Formation of rose-pink colour with the ammonical layer indicates the presence of anthranol glycosides.

Legal's Test: Plant -Extracts were treated with sodium nitropruside in pyridine and sodium hydroxide solution. Formation of pink to blood red colour shows the presence of cardiac glycosides.

3. Detection of saponins

a) Froth Test: Plant -Extracts were diluted with distilled water to make 20ml and this was shaken in a graduated cylinder for around 15 minutes. Formation of 1 cm layer of foam in the solution indicates the presence of saponins.

b) Foam Test: 0.5 gm of plant -extracts was shaken with 2 ml of water. If foam produced remains for ten minutes it indicates the presence of saponins.

4. Detection of phenols

Ferric Chloride Test: Plant -Extracts were treated with 3-4 drops of ferric chloride solution. Formation of bluish black colour shows the presence of phenols in a solution.

5. Detection of tannins

Gelatin Test: To the plant - extract, 1% gelatin solution containing sodium chloride was added. Formation of white precipitate shows the presence of tannins in a solution.

6. Detection of flavonoids

a) Alkaline Reagent Test: Plant -Extracts were treated with few drops of sodium hydroxide solution. Formation of intense yellow colour, which becomes colourless on addition of dilute acid, shows the presence of flavonoids in a solution.

b) *Lead* acetate Test: Plant -Extracts were treated with few drops of lead acetate solution. Formation of yellow colour precipitate shows the presence of flavonoids in a solution.

7. Detection of diterpenes

Copper acetate Test: Plant -Extracts were dissolved in water and treated with 3-4 drops of copper acetate solution. Formation of emerald green colour shows the presence of diterpenes in a solution.

Observation & Result:

Phytochemical screening: Phytochemical screening of *Borehaaviadiffusa* powder revealed the presence of flavonoids, alkaloids;coumarins, tannins, while glycosides steroids , and saponins were absent.

Table: II Alcoholic Extraction of *Borehaavia diffusa*

Sr. No.	Test of Phytochemicals	Alcoholic Extraction of <i>Borehaaviadiffusa</i> (Methanol)
1	Alkaloids	+
2	Glycosides	-
3	Saponins	-
4	Phenols	+
5	Tannins	+
6	Flavonoids	+
7	Triterpenoids	+
8	Steroids	-
9	Coumarins	+
(Present: +, Absent: -)		

Table: III Alcoholic Extraction of *Tribulus terrestris*

Sr. No.	Test of Phytochemicals	Leaves Extracts of <i>Tribulus terrestris</i> (Methanol)
1	Alkaloids	+
2	Glycosides	+
3	Saponins	+
4	Phenols	+
5	Tannins	+
6	Flavonoids	+
7	Terpenoids	+
(Present: +, Absent: -)		

Conclusion:

Boerhaavia diffusa and *Tribulus terrestris*, both are mainly used for treating the disorders of kidneys, some common Bio active compounds are responsible for the curing the kidney disorders. Phytochemical screening of Secondary metabolites of both the plants will be helpful to find out the common of Phytochemical compounds. By controlling the soil conditions bioactive compounds can be obtained in larger quantity, which will helpful for further researchers in finding a highly efficient natural drug for kidney patients without any side effects. Instead of going for Dialysis or kidney transplant people can have efficient drug for better recovery.

Suggestions:

Boerhaavia diffusa and *Tribulus terrestris*, both are mainly used for treating the disorders of kidneys, some common Bio active compounds are responsible for the curing the kidney disorders. Phytochemical screening of Secondary metabolites of both the plants will be helpful to find out the common of Phytochemical compounds. By controlling the soil conditions bioactive compounds can be obtained in larger quantity, which will helpful for further researchers in finding a

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